

DESCRIPTIVE-REFERENCE METHOD: A NEW METHOD FOR THE STUDY OF POLICY

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Arthur Gomes Dau

Master in Administration and professor at UNIPAC-Barbacena. arthurgdau@gmail.com

Sandro Dau

Post-Doctor in Philosophy and author of several books in the areas of Politics, Scientific Methodology and Philosophy. sandrodau2008@gmail.com

Sergio Rodrigues de Souza

Political Scientist. sergiorodrigues52@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

This article is about the Descriptive-Referential Method, a new methodology for studying politics from a systematic understanding. Its scientific relevance is presented in the sense of presenting and clarifying to the public of Applied Social Sciences a new proposal for the synthesis of political thought as a pragmatic target-object. Its social relevance is shown in the parameters of expanding the potential of understanding politics as an element of social character, inherent to the human being. This is a bibliographic, factual, descriptive research. What the author seeks to do is to give a scientific character to the study of power and trace the path of its attainment, from the local sphere to the control of the Dominant Political Organization. According to his prism of analysis, the great difficulty in investigating power is the lack of a specific method, which can shed light on the darkness in which its study finds itself. In order to achieve this he creates a new method for studying power: the Descriptive-Referential Method. This is characterized by the study of ideas, leaders, states and political communications. It is a method that must be used from the smallest part of political action: the leader.

Keywords: Politics; Descriptive-Referential Method; Political science.

INTRODUCTION

At a time when intellectual speculations reach a burning point in politics, when the Modern National State enters into decadence, with the emergence of large supranational blocs

and the individual is placed at the center of political power, Bonifácio de Andrada's theoretical effort is to identify the action of the new leaders in the construction of this new society: however, it is worth mentioning that the author abandons the moral connotation until then dominant in the study of power relations and is guided by his scientific-naturalistic verve.

Before continuing, it is urgent to ask a question: what is power? By answering this question, which for centuries has been studied, analyzed, scrutinized, etc., the author is able to perceive how few have had the courage to admit: that it is an individual's own quality, which he puts into practice whenever necessary. perform a public task. In addition to this founding mark, power is also manifested in convincing, forcing, in imposing their interests on individuals. In this sense, we can argue that power is a quality that the individual has to predominate over others, aiming to articulate them in order to form a dominant group, whose ultimate objective is the maintenance and expansion of their own power. Power is a quality and its origin is in the individual: "It is verified, therefore, that the phenomenon of Power is an articulation of people, and these create social facts, around a leadership, which will express the interest of the group and, through this fact, the creation of States or Empires will or will not occur" (ANDRADA, 2000, p. 16).

THE ORIGIN OF THE DESCRIPTIVE-REFERENCE METHOD

When Bonifácio de Andrada (2000) uses the Descriptive-Referential Method, it aims to produce the unmasking of power. The author does this because power is the very element of his life, leading him to several questions and, therefore, ended up being his object of study par excellence.

In order to study this object, he developed the Descriptive-Referential Method , which favors the understanding of power in a wide field of possibilities. The author starts from the presupposition of Aristotle (799-737 before Hypatia) that "every science can be taught and its object learned". Thus, when presenting the Descriptive-Referential Method, he shows that the study of power is no longer an aspect of the life of intellectuals or the action of the elite and places it within the reach of all individuals.

This method, when studying power, does so both in its theoretical and practical aspects, because the author's objective is not only to create a method for the delight of his

intellectual, but to establish a scientific knowledge that can serve as a bridge to knowledge of the policy in order to obtain a more efficient action.

But why does Bonifácio de Andrada want to create a method for studying politics? Because a renewal of political values can only be possible when knowledge about reality is renewed. More than interpreting political actions, the author wants to present why these actions occur in this way and not in another way, therefore he proposes changes in the conduct of individuals. With the Descriptive-Referential Method, we seek to discover why individuals act: this is the political realism of the author who intends to defend civil society from dictatorships that are always on the alert.

This method is formed by a set of techniques, which seeks to discover the detailed references of power existing in society. It is a study that aims to know the theories, techniques, communications and structures that support the actions of leaders, their political communications and the leader's ultimate goal: the structuring of global political actions.

What the author seeks to do is to give a scientific character to the study of power and trace the path of its attainment, from the local sphere to the control of the Dominant Political Organization. According to his prism of analysis, the great difficulty in investigating power is the lack of a specific method, which can shed light on the darkness in which its study finds itself: this has as an immediate consequence the confusion in the analyses, in the actions and solutions, because when scientists face these elements, they cannot separate them from Philosophy, Sociology, Administration, Law, Anthropology and so on.

Therefore, there is an urgent need to create a method that makes it possible to understand the object of Political Science (power), so that it is possible to envision solutions to the practical issues of everyday life. This is the author's theoretical proposal: to create a method that is capable of studying power, in its main characteristics, in a broad way (without losing sight of the multiple particularities) and in depth (always returning to the aspects of common life). And by proposing this new method, he is trying to ground Politics as a Science, in order to escape the multitude of baseless opinions: only with this intellectual and practical attitude will it be possible to understand and change this important aspect of the life of individuals in society.

In order to achieve this he devises a new method for studying power: the Descriptive-Referential Method. This is characterized by the study of ideas, leaders, states and political communications. It is a method that must be used from the smallest part of political action: the leader.

And why does this method come from the leader? The answer can be seen in Niccolò Machiavelli (1054-1112 after Hypatia): “The desire to conquer is natural and common, and men capable of doing so will always be praised, never criticized” (MAQUIAVEL, 1999, p. 47).).

After defining the object of Political Science, delimiting its field of action and the means by which power should be studied, Bonifácio de Andrada begins by tracing the general characteristics of his method; the main one is the search for basic references that can describe the relevant aspects of power: “The Descriptive-Referential Method is one that seeks to describe, explain, inform in an objective way about the political phenomenon, locating in it points of reference, to from there, proceed to its description and subsequent explanation and interpretation” (ANDRADA, 1998, p. 22).

THE OBJECTIVES OF THE DESCRIPTIVE-REFERENCE METHOD

The Descriptive-Referential Method seeks to describe the most varied references of power, in order to unite them in a broad political theory, which serves to solve localized problems. To do so, he analyses, decomposes and synthesizes its manifestations: it shows the rational path that must be followed, based on human experience, its power relations and its subsequent empirical confirmation.

With the Descriptive-Referential Method, the study of power focuses on the action of the leader, who has a quality (moral, spiritual, economic, social or any other imaginable) that is more prominent than the other individuals around him. It is the study of this action and how it transforms the social that is the objective of this method, because only by understanding how the leader acts, to impose his interests, is it possible to understand how a society exists.

Therefore, its objective is to discuss the possibility of the leader making his desires submit to the desires of other members of society. For Bonifácio de Andrada , when studying power it is necessary to start from Micropolitics, because it is in the actions of the leader that the answers to the phenomenon of power will be found.

The entire Descriptive-Referential Method is concerned with explaining the birth, achievement and action of the leader in achieving and maintaining power. With this method, the important thing is to identify who has the quality to assume power and, for that, it is necessary to seek their existence in the concrete social relations of individuals and not in theoretical abstractions, which exist only in the reflections of theoretical thinkers.

For the author, politics is the study of the horizon of the quality of the individual. Politics in this sense is within its qualitative dynamics, however each society has its own political foundation and the Descriptive-Referential Method will seek to study how power presents itself in the most varied situations not worrying about a generalizing theory about power, the leader, political communication, or the state.

This method allows a detailed study of the leader's conduct in its most varied aspects: knowledge, communication and collective organization. A very important aspect that the Descriptive-Referential Method points out to us is that the leader's domination cannot be massive, closed, monolithic, because if that is the case, the leader will no longer be in the political environment, but in that of slavery, or servitude. Politics is the world of free men and being free means making choices without coercion, says Bonifácio de Andrada.

He proposes to study the daily practice of individuals in order to establish possible laws of political behavior. Referring the results of the Descriptive-Referential Method to the theoretical assumption that the essence of political action is power. Thus, its objectives are theoretical-pragmatic in trying to identify, analyze, justify and modify political facts.

THE DESCRIPTIVE-REFERENCE METHOD AND OTHER METHODS OF STUDYING THE POLICY

It goes without saying that his method differs from other traditional methods of studying politics, both in terms of the multiplicity of conditions for analyzing power and in terms of the very definition of power as a quality of the leader.

The assumption of this quality is the first moment, envisioned by the author, in the conduction of the led. He knows that individuals are unpredictable, yet he still wants to describe, understand their social actions based on the interpretation of references from their daily lives. With this he wants to find some points, which are invariable in some aspects, so it can be said that he wants to create a Science of political behavior.

For Bonifácio de Andrada, it is urgent to locate the main points of political action, such as: leadership, communications, Dominant Political Organizations and doctrines. The difference between his method and other methods, such as Historical Materialism, is that he looks at political events and not at economic events; he is concerned with modifying the present society and not building one in the future; he desires the reality of life and not the ideality of death. This explains why the Descriptive-Referential Method is richer, in its political interpretations, than all existing methods in Political Science.

Bonifácio de Andrada assumes that power is a complex phenomenon, so he recommends using a complex research method, however easy to apply. He uses the Descriptive-Referential Method as a way of escaping the confusions in which other researchers find themselves, since they do not use a method that can cover all the specifics of the object of Political Science. Therefore, when he analyzes power, in current societies, he advises pursuing three paths:

1. Find your top references;
2. Describe them as faithfully as possible;
3. Make the eidetic reduction, that is, abandon political prejudices, in order to find the essence of the phenomenon of power.²⁵

This Method is a radicalization of the study of power, in which the author admits his dependence on the quality of the leader. In this view, it is the leader who will set power in motion and build, through his interests, the great political institutions for the well-being of individuals. It is an attempt to describe power in all its specificity and not just in one aspect: economic, religious, moral, and so on.

This method is a critique of all previous forms of study of power, seeking to show how power was, until then, approached in a naive way. In it, power is not the result of History, Society, Religion, Economy, the will of a good-natured god or the uncoordinated actions of an individual, but originated in the interest, needs and tastes of the leader himself.

Bonifácio de Andrada wants to present the leader as the guide of laws, truths, lies and other aspects that are part of the State. For him, it is the leader who creates the strategies, which coordinate the actions in the public space. We cannot fail to draw attention to the fact that every leader's action is only possible if it is supported by other individuals.

The Descriptive-Referential Method seeks to know the actions of leaders by ordering them in such a way that they can constitute their actions into valid theories for Political Science. The role of the Method is to oppose any attempt to study power without scientific rigor and without pre-established objectives. It is, therefore, an opposition to the amateurism of would-be researchers, with little theoretical-practical basis, who prefer the tranquility of the repetition of jargon to the courage to transform the truths conveniently maintained by the tradition of subalternity.

²⁵Bonifácio de Andrada is developing yet another work in which he uses the concept of eidetic dereduction, that is, he seeks to find the place where power should be analyzed. In this way, it will move from theory to practice (Authors' Note, 2022).

The author realized that the existing methods of studying power are not able to express the complexity of the individual's life, both internal (ethical) and external (political). Thus, both Economics is important in research on power, as is knowledge of the morals of individuals, the identification of their ideas, their speeches, as it is also necessary to look at large political institutions, large and small. leaders.

Of all the methods used to study political relations, the one that provides more conditions to understand them, while allowing us to change reality, is the Descriptive-Referential Method, as it is concerned with the leader's action, with their ideas, with the institutionalization of power by the leadership and with communication, aiming to achieve, destroy, or maintain power.

In this way, the author traces his perception of power in a meridian way, as he knows that power is not only a war, coercion, co-optation and/or division, but also a dialogue, a conviction, a group of hopes, a set of doubts and an enormity of yearnings. From this perspective, the Descriptive-Referential Method surpasses all others, as it seeks to understand power in a greater number of possible perspectives, in order to offer a greater number of possibilities for structuring or de-structuring a society.

THE POWER AND THE DESCRIPTIVE-REFERENCE METHOD

presentation, discussion and analysis of the Descriptive-Referential Method can be found in *Political Science* by Bonifácio de Andrada . For the author, the goal of all politics is power, yet a power that is accessible to everyone and not just to a few enlightened, or chosen. Power for him is a quality of the individual and as such it should be studied independently of other phenomena that exist in their lives:

Power is understood as the ability to dominate a situation, political power is in promoting the articulation of people to form dominant social groups. Such agglutination creates a collective will expressed by a leadership that leads the grouping, resulting in the emergence of a social force that, in a certain way, intimidates and coerces [as it also acts through dialogicity] and, therefore, within the community, makes obeyed, assuming its direction and organizing itself to definitively prevail (ANDRADA, 2013, p. 13).

In his works on the Descriptive-Referential Method, the author tries to explain how the phenomenon of power should be studied, because according to his words, this is a multiplicity of qualitative relations, which are immanent in the places where these relations occur.

The author states that the power relationship does not happen through the rules of Logic, since if **A** obeys **B** ; if **C** obeys **A** ; it cannot be inferred that **C** obeys **B**. With this approach he transposes the study of Politics from pure theory to practice:

It will be studies of this type that will show us specific realities in the political fact and can be taken to political technique to promote their practices on how to overcome problems. In fact, the political technique or political practice is a permanent demand of society in the effort to overcome the obstacles that are always surrounding Power (ANDRADA, 2013, p. 14).

His method seeks to study power where it occurs and, therefore, wants to study, analyze and present solutions to local and immediate political problems. Drawing on Max Weber (1459-1515 after Hypatia), he states that the hallmark of power is domination. However, he takes the German sociologist a step further and claims that power is self-domination, because when studying Aristotle, Bonifácio de Andrada learned from an early age that only those who manage to dominate themselves can dominate others.

It is impossible to abandon the perspective that power is found in the State and in the Law, says the Descriptive-Referential Method, since they are part of political life in the West and always appear as an evident and unquestionable truth. However, perceiving it only from this perspective is to make it unsustainable, so this method will privilege the investigation not only of the social class as well as the leader; nor will he be content to reflect on theories, since he understands that the practice of power is the *conditio sine qua non* for its existence; will look with unprecedented depth at communications without forgetting the voice of the leaders. Seen from this angle, the Descriptive-Referential Method is one of the most complete, powerful and efficient tools that have been produced in the last five hundred years in the study of power .

In every social relationship, says the author, it is possible to find some aspects that serve as references for the understanding of power:

- The conduct of society;
 - The set of ideas that are adopted;
 - The group that manages to predominate in a certain place;
 - The communication maintained between the leadership and those being led
- (ANDRADA, 2013, p. 16).

The author makes a sweeping revelation when he presents the Descriptive-Referential Method: power is also violence, because to eliminate violence from the human world is to

abandon that world; it exists and, as such, it must be studied not to end it (since that would be a utopia), but to avoid having to use it unnecessarily (the need for its use will always exist, when the power of the individual , or State, is threatened).

LEADERSHIP AND THE DESCRIPTIVE REFERENCE METHOD

In this way, the Descriptive-Referential Method shows that the individual, in order to achieve his goal, that is, increase and maintain his power, must increase knowledge about the basic needs of citizens. It is up to the leader to manage these needs and the movements of individuals, so he needs to develop various political techniques.

When knowledge is introduced into the world of politics, it delimits one of the characteristics of the leader, that is, to enable greater social well-being, as a consequence, it increases its own power over society, at the same time that it increases the power of society itself. society.

It is the leaders who, acting in society, can change state and/or individual political elements using qualified knowledge for such action. With the possession of effective knowledge for a given situation, the leader exercises power over the members of the local group and increases their strength until reaching the limits of the large Dominant Political Organizations.

The Descriptive-Referential Method wants to identify the functioning of power in society in the action of individuals. It is illuminating that this method refers to the individual, who practices a certain action as a creator of power: a power that creates desires, tastes, bodies and knowledge, going from the individual to the State as well as from the State to the individual, passing through their communication and if structuring through theories.

The author intends to affirm that, in order to understand power, it is necessary to observe the leader's relations with the other members of society. It is these relationships that will build political institutions, which will materialize the interests of the leader and his followers.

He wants to discover the origin of the leader's power, to know what are the conditions for moving, or maintaining control of a society. The Descriptive Referential Method seeks to highlight the main references of the leader's action and describe them, in order to generalize his actions. In this way, it starts from the leader's own analysis, studying certain references that produce specific and specific results. Bonifácio de Andrada doesn't want to simply

describe the leader's social life, he without obstacles wants to highlight the values and ideas that form him.

Therefore, in the Descriptive-Referential Method, the focus is on the individual, who, having a persistent personality, risks modifying social relations: it is for this reason that the author places him as the central point of his analyses.

He shows that the aspirations of the leaders impose a political economy on other individuals; this action will only be relevant if it submits other individuals and puts consciously elaborated ideas into practice. In this way, power is exercised from the leader, who, in order to materialize his ideals, uses a set of elements not only of a moral but also of a material and technical nature, which sustain his power in relation to others. It is the leader's moral behavior that will give him the condition of dominance and the possibility of changing or maintaining a political reality. Thus, Bonifácio de Andrada builds a method that makes it possible to study power and discover it in the actions of each leader: there is no power without a leader, because all power depends on his effective presence. Any and all statements that take the power out of the leader's hands and place him in society, in the class, in God, are either childish behavior or clever trickery.

In summary, it is possible to say that the author proposes a more efficient way of studying power, or better, analyzing it from the political experiences of leaders. His attention is placed on the leaders and he studies their interrelationships, seeking as many references as possible, which can be described, in order to understand the phenomenon of power.

As can be seen, the action of the leader, in the creation of the State, is not based on principles external to the political world: at the moment of this creation, the leader must be guided by his own qualities. In this way, if his objective is the consolidation of the State, he must use his power, to reassure, to organize, to administer and to guide his followers.

THE INFLUENCES OF EDMUND HUSSERL ON THE DESCRIPTIVE-REFERENCE METHOD

Bonifácio de Andrada in the construction of Politics as Science first creates a method: the Descriptive-Referential Method. This method starts from the Phenomenology of Edmund Husserl (1889-1958 after Hypatia), as it grounds the necessary conditions for the clarification of the phenomenon and, more precisely, of the phenomenon of power. In addition, Phenomenology allows identifying the limits, essence and influence of power within society.

Its Method was “inspired by the phenomenological view, in which it seeks to describe the phenomenon positively, in order to be fully informed about it so that it can highlight its main items or aspects” (ANDRADA, 2003, p. 13). By using Phenomenology as a starting point, he wants to describe, as clearly as possible, the concretization of power through its main referential aspects, leading to enlightening conclusions about the political facts of the society studied.

The phenomenological observation is necessary, because power is located in political reality: this power arises within society, however when it is set in motion by the individual, it acquires *a certain personalization* and becomes an object of study quite distinct from others, since it has an autonomous existence.

Edmund Husserl's phenomenological method is concerned with studying things in detail in order to identify their essence. This is what he calls eidetic reduction: “The essence will be the result of an operation of thought in which the representation of the thing, the representation of beings, in abstract terms, is sought, so that this representation serves for the understanding of all others. similar entities” (ANDRADA, 2003, p. 106).

In Edmund Husserl's phenomenology, essences are of two kinds: Exact and Vague or morphological. The first type of essence is linked to the so-called Exact Sciences, while the second type refers to the concrete existence of things.

When studying power using the phenomenological method, it must be placed in the field of morphological essences, as these exist in the concreteness of History. For this reason, Bonifácio de Andrada starts from Edmund Husserl's Phenomenological Theory, in order to study the most varied characteristics of power, located in a certain "historical situation". The Descriptive-Referential Method is a complement to Edmund Husserl's theory in relation to the understanding of the world of politics, as it facilitates scholars to understand the phenomenon of power:

And to understand power as a morphological essence, as a vague essence, the technique adopted by the thinker is precisely the descriptive one, seeking to describe the phenomenon as much as possible so that it can be understood, so that it can be understood in this effort of description of exploration. of power, to absorb it with its eidetic reduction and reach, in fact, its true essence, its authentic essence (ANDRADA, 2003, p. 107).

Bonifácio de Andrada states that, when power is focused through the lens of essence, some points immediately arise, which allow their identification by the researcher. The first relevant point perceived when looking at power through essence is that it is a quality of an

individual: this quality surpasses him and the local group is formed; in this case too, power goes beyond the group and the group ends up identifying itself with the State.

Power as a relationship between individuals is placed in that space, which Edmund Husserl called the intersubjectivity of *selves*. This author places the subject as the center of the search for the essence: it is for this reason that Bonifácio de Andrada wants to study power, based on Husserlian phenomenology, since power is placed within the scope of intersubjectivity. The Descriptive-Referential Method, when approaching power, does so as follows:

Thus, the essence of singular cases of manifestations of political power is advanced, taking into account the existence of the specific pieces that surround it, the conditions of its realization and, above all, the valorization of certain moments of the phenomenon of power, to provide the Political Science basic points for its analysis in the existential reality (ANDRADA, 2003, pp. 110-111).

After identifying the essence of power, the Descriptive-Referential Method requires moving to the historical environment in which it is possible to understand how power acts in political reality:

Here we have to go a little further than the vision of essence because it gives us, as it were, the representative synthesis of the phenomenon of substance, when now we need to find data linked to existence that is richer, more pluralistic than essence, as yet knowing the aspects of valuation, in the moments in which the phenomenon of power unfolds or develops (ANDRADA, 2003, p. 109).

The Descriptive-Referential Method is important for Political Science, since it is through phenomenological analysis that the multiple variations of power can be assimilated, and one must study the values of society and its relations with power, from, of course, , of political existence.

With this method, the essence of power is reached, while paving the way for the understanding of its various existential aspects, which are present in the plane of History and, as such, it is the place where the individual has several specificities, including politics.

In this way, when searching for the essence of power, the Descriptive-Referential Method makes use of the Phenomenological Theory, as this is an adequate instrument to find the references of power and to describe them. However, this method also uses the Theory of Values and the Existentialist Theory, since power is a value that exists in society.

When Bonifácio de Andrada uses the term valuation, he is aware that this concept is linked to the Theory of Values, since a reference of political power is the concretization of

social values. This position extends John Locke's worldview, who saw political power as a voluntary agreement, which is granted “to rulers for the benefit of their subjects, in order to secure them the possession and use of property” (LOCKE, 2000). , p. 103). While the English author understands political power as having the purpose of protecting property, Bonifácio de Andrada shows that the purpose of this power is broader and what is important is the realization of the leader's own values that are reflected in society, as well as the guarantee of all the properties that John Locke well defended.

THE METHODOLOGICAL PROCEDURES OF THE DESCRIPTIVE-REFERENCE METHOD

The first step suggested by Bonifácio de Andrada is to collect data related to political action; second, it will be done through a rigorous description of the way in which power occurs in society; finally, the researcher should generalize the standard manifestations of power in society through rules.

The Descriptive-Referential Method seeks to encompass both the ideas that move the leader, as well as the communication that is necessary for him to maintain, or increase, his power, in addition to which he will be concerned with the relationships existing at the heart of the State.

As we can see, this is a Method concerned with the origins, functioning, dynamics, structuring and communication of the power phenomenon: starting from Micropolitics (the leader's action) in an upward movement, with the objective of showing how the leader's interests change the behavior of the whole society.

This innovative Method unites several techniques for studying political behavior in the dispute for control of dominant political structures; it identifies how political ideas are arranged in macropolitical and micropolitical space, as well as how they are communicated to society.

By using this method, the researcher aims to understand what is random not in the action of power (because all power has only one objective: to preserve itself), but in the political action of the leader, aspiring to the understanding of political phenomena. It allows the researcher's gaze to hover over the specifics of the action of the leader and those who are led, with the objective of knowing the political dynamics: it is a Method that is concerned with the techniques, strategies and tactics that privilege the complex movement of relations of power.

The importance of this method – it cannot be repeated too often – is present from the moment the researcher's attention is directed both to the State and to the individual, both in terms of ideas and political communication. The Descriptive-Referential Method prescribes that power should be studied not only in the State, but in its other forms of manifestation: through the study of ideas, the author advocates the understanding of the theoretical-referential framework that sustains the leader's attitudes; with the research on leadership, he wants to delve into concrete life; through the analysis of communications, he hopes to perceive the nuances that form power relations; by means of the deepening of the study on the State, he wants to unveil its guiding character.

Its importance lies in the fact that with it we learn that the phenomenon of power is an eternal action in society. With it, it is possible to study the way in which power acts not only in the State but also in leaderships, ideas and their communications: it is a Method that immerses the researcher in the world of human relations where they occur.

It is the Descriptive-Referential Method of such great complexity and depth that putting it into practice, even in a small society, would become a Herculean task. Anticipating these difficulties in its execution, Bonifácio de Andrada proposed its division into several techniques (with the didactic purpose of its learning and application), since political life cannot be sliced and understood in isolation into its parts. By proposing this Method, the author wants to offer Politics a rational scheme that shows how power is played out in the world: hence, he presents us with the four defining techniques of his Method: Metapolitics; Micropolitics; Macropolitics; Nunciopolitics.

The first form is identified as the set of ideas used by the leader in order to conquer political command; the second is related to the study of the leader's action in the pursuit of guiding tactics of political conduct and with its operating mechanics; with regard to Macropolitics, it is the field in which the leader will move from local domination to national domination; finally, we have Nunciopolitics, which is concerned with the analysis of political communications.

By indicating these four techniques, the author manages to touch on the neuralgic point of the study of power: power must be understood as an inherent quality and constructed by the individual himself. With the Descriptive-Referential Method he shows that it is necessary to scientifically organize the study of power in all its aspects referring to the complex political process existing in human societies.

Within this context, the method for studying power must focus on the existential multiplicity of individuals present in social relations. Because power does not manifest itself only in the organic structures of the State, but similarly through an infinity of small movements (Micropolitics) and large movements (Macropolitics) using a whole set of theories, which support or not a certain idea (Metapolitics) and , finally, making use of existing discourses among the various members of a political community (Nunciopolitics).

When making this division, however, the author does it more for didactic reasons, since it is impossible to study power isolating it in each part: it is this perception of the author that differentiates him from other political thinkers, since they saw only a few aspects of power. He is aware that in making this division, he does not intend to make each part irreducible to the other, much less to deny the complexity of each one. The objective of this division is the observation, description, analysis, synthesis and classification of social relations that may interest Political Science: this objective will occur when we manage to describe the points of reference of power relations.

Having made this first approach, phenomenological analysis must find the primary references of power, that is, the ideas and doctrines that move leaders or groups. And that's not all, because Bonifácio de Andrada's Method requires analyzing the institutional consolidation of power and the way in which this institutionalization is communicated to individuals. In summary, it is necessary to find the guiding ideas (Metapolitics), then observe how they are used by the leader (Micropolitics), in a third moment, see the consolidation of these theories (Macropolitics) and finally their communication (Nunciopolitics):

These elements are the points of reference that we arrive at after that overview that phenomenology authorizes us, to identify the essence of power and immediately the fundamental or referential points of this essence that will allow us to assume the knowledge that we want to really achieve, with the existentialist methodology, the capture or efficient perception of political reality, later (ANDRADA, 2003, p. 114).

The study of power before the Descriptive-Referential Method was *unitary* , as the authors sought to study it on a single aspect: force, war, repression, domination, economy, religion, culture, society, and so on. With this new method, research on power relations becomes multiple, since the author emphasizes the need to study the different ways in which they could be approached. His wish is to make it clear that there is no specific approach to power, but there are polymorphic ways of studying it.

The author was never attracted by the dream of building a perfect method, however he was concerned with outlining its main subjects, clarifying its multiple aspects and offering a

new method with which to understand this object, which so fascinates individuals: political power. .

Bonifácio de Andrada wants through the Descriptive-Referential Method to find points that can serve as references to power and describe them in order to know how political action is developed. Its conclusions deserve the status of Science, because they are not merely descriptions of the political fact: they are an elaboration that goes through the descriptive empirical prism and goes to the theorization about the leader's conduct in society.

The task proposed by the Descriptive-Referential Method is immense, since it admits the study of different fields of politics, discovering that domination passes through the great apparatuses of the State and the actions of local leaders; for this reason, it is necessary to research how the leader manages to stand out in relation to other individuals.

He wants with his Descriptive-Referential Method to analyze the knowledge possessed, used, created and manipulated by leaders, so that he can offer the minimum conditions necessary for individuals to become free. Without choice, this freedom passes through Political Science, which, with Bonifácio Andrada, becomes the understanding of knowledge, which constitutes the practical actions of leaders. In other words, the freedom of the individual is directly linked to the local knowledge that he dominates in the construction of his political environment.

His Method privileges the study of political communication: he begins by stating that it must be free, since different political opinions help to maintain freedom against arbitrary governments. In this sense, he agrees with Benjamin Constant, who argued that arbitrariness is incompatible with the existence of a government conceived as an institution. It is the extreme opposite of the social contract, undermining every political institution at its base; it is dangerous for a government, because it always deprives its activity of regularity and continuity, not serving, as far as security is concerned, as its defenders say.

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